

THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN THE FORMATION OF PERSONALITY

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ABSTRACT

A music teacher must know not only his subject, but also philosophy, aesthetics, psychology, pedagogy well and be able to apply it in his work. One of the most difficult problems of pedagogy is to fully convey the impact of music, its essence to the minds of children. A music teacher must form the following qualities in children in the lessons of "Musical Culture": Friendship, patriotism, loyalty, kindness, hard work, initiative, etc.

The development of singing skills in children has its own difficulties. Children are not yet able to fully analyze the work. Therefore, first of all, the musical director himself should sing the song in an exemplary manner. If the song is recorded on tape, then playing the song on a tape recorder performed by a children's choir also gives good results. Then the song is memorized by singing it over and over again. There are two conditions for the re-singing method:

1) The child must have thorough, accurate knowledge of what exactly he should do and what he can achieve when singing.

2) The child must know what he has achieved, what results each exercise gave, what mistakes were made, and must eliminate mistakes in subsequent exercises.

We recommend you to use some of them during training. "Circle" method In this, students sit in a circle and perform various exercises.[1] In order to properly fulfill the first condition, it is necessary to pay attention to the connection of the process of musical literacy with the process of singing, their logical correspondence. The fulfillment of the second condition depends on whether the re-singing exercise is aimed at a specific goal. In this case, the music director (teacher) should analyze the exercise with the children in a timely manner each time it is re-sung. In order to achieve good results in singing, it is recommended that the music director (teacher) conduct the following activities:

- 1) To make children feel harmony;
- 2) Take into account the individual characteristics of each child;
- 3) Use national musical instruments as much as possible;

4) Involve talented children who actively participate in lessons in music circles.

In music classes, children are not limited to learning songs or mastering musical rhythmic movements, but also listen to and perceive musical works performed by the music director (teacher) and using technical means. Explaining and introducing the basics of music to children expands the level of musical knowledge of children. Listening to musical compositions enriches the content of classes, increases their variety, and greatly contributes to making classes more exciting.

Children answer as best they can. The music director (teacher) shows the children Uzbek national musical instruments with the help of visual aids, introduces them one by one, and exchanges ideas with the children. He recommends that children participate in circles to be able to play musical instruments.

As we can see, the music director (teacher) must not only be able to sing, but also have a number of musical and theoretical knowledge. Music classes, whether it is singing, listening to music, or theoretical knowledge, lay the foundation for the formation of the younger generation as a fully developed person, embodying moral purity, spiritual wealth and physical perfection.

Music is an art form that occupies a wide place in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of the human personality. Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of aesthetic education, teaching people to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around them. Music equips a person with a high taste and forms a spiritual worldview. Music has the ability to have a strong impact on human emotions, introducing students to the world of aesthetics and is an important means of moral and ideological education. The ancestor of our national culture, Abu-Nasir Al-Farabi, said: "This science is useful for the health of the body." Our grandfather, Sheikh Saadi, said: "Music is the companion of the human soul." Music is a tool that actively develops emotional feelings that quickly affect a person. A person gets acquainted with music through his mother, and finds pleasure and support from music throughout his life. Music is considered an integral part of the human psyche. To receive various nourishment from music, a person must be highly cultured, have a pure heart, be able to feel beauty, and have love for his profession and his Motherland. Therefore, the main goal of music education is to cultivate musical culture in students, which is a component of human spirituality. To achieve this high goal, the tasks set for the music teacher are as follows:

1. To increase interest and love for the art of music in students.
2. To develop artistic creativity and feelings in the process of musical activities.
3. To educate students morally and aesthetically through the artistic and ideological content of works.
4. In music lessons, it is necessary to carry out work such as instilling in students a passion for the profession and labor.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[2]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.PD -3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and

“Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [3] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD -4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [4].

The implementation of these goals and objectives depends on the professional and moral image of the teacher. Not every artist can teach music lessons at school. To do this, a music teacher must be a highly cultured, broad-minded, spiritually mature person who loves his profession and children, and can skillfully play any musical instrument. He must have in-depth knowledge of pedagogy, psychology, child physiology, ethics and aesthetics theory, practical areas of music theory, and music teaching methodology. A music teacher must have sufficient knowledge, skills, and experience in the theoretical and practical areas of musical art. That is, a music teacher is also an instrumentalist and singer. He must work as a choir conductor, conductor, music theorist, and practitioner. The creativity of a music teacher is that he acts as the author of the script for an hour-long lesson, its performer and director. Therefore, a music lesson is called an art lesson. The scope of activity of a music teacher in school life is wide.[5]

The contribution of music to the development of our nation is incomparable. As an independent state, we have risen to the world podium among the countries of the world. We have recognized our state as spiritual and enlightening. Music plays an important role in raising the consciousness of future generations. Music has not only cultural, but also political and social significance, and we must feel how responsible it is. Paying attention to everything from high creative examples to national folklore, we realize that music serves the people and their interests. The dreams, hopes and aspirations of the people are reflected in melodies and songs. If we pay attention to national traditions and values, we can see how ancient and developed music is in all historical works, from war songs to epics. The fate of heroes like Alpomish and Gorogly has been sung in a whole new way for thousands of years. We know from history that six of the masterpieces of Shashmakom have survived to our time, and that twelve maqams were performed by Muhammad Ali Mashshak.[6] These masterpieces, which have played an important role in the spiritual development of Uzbeks and all Eastern peoples, are only a part of our musical art. The fact that the ghazals composed for Shashmakom are the wisdom of our ancestors, especially the ghazals of Navoi and other thinkers, further inspires respect for the past of our nation. We feel how great their spirituality was. It is our honorable duty to create songs that glorify patriotism, goodness, justice, and beauty, and to teach them to the new generation so that the melodies and songs created now can effectively serve our nation. The teacher is the leader in ensuring the effectiveness of music education and in cultivating students' interest in music lessons.

Music is an art form that occupies a wide place in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of human personality. Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of elegance, teaching people to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around them. Music equips a person with a high taste and forms a spiritual worldview. Music has the ability to have a strong impact on human emotions, introducing students to the world of elegance and is an important means of moral and ideological education. The ancestor of our national culture, Abu-Nasir Al-Farabi, said: “This science is useful for the health of the body.” Our grandfather, Sheikh Sadi, said: “Music is the

companion of the human soul.” Music is a means of actively developing emotional feelings that quickly affect a person. A person gets acquainted with music through his mother, and finds pleasure and support from music throughout his life. Music is an integral part of the human psyche. In order to receive various nourishment from music, a person must be highly cultured, have a pure heart, be able to feel beauty, and have love for his profession and his Motherland. Therefore, the main goal of music education is to cultivate musical culture in students, which is a component of human spirituality.[7] To achieve this high goal, the tasks set for the music teacher are as follows:

To increase interest and love for the art of music in students. To develop artistic creativity and feelings in the process of musical activities. To educate students morally and aesthetically through the artistic and ideological content of works.

In music lessons, it is necessary to carry out activities such as instilling enthusiasm in students for their profession and labor. Through this activity, children learn to feel the melody, tempo, and rhythm of music.[8]

The contribution of music to the development of our nation is incomparable. As an independent state, we have risen to the world podium among the countries of the world. We have recognized our state as spiritual and educational. Music plays an important role in raising the consciousness of future generations. Music has not only cultural, but also political and social significance, and we must feel how responsible it is. As we pay attention to high creative examples and national folklore. We realize that music serves the people and their interests. The strength lies in the fact that he calls for the development of music not only to experience itself, but also to the use of science and scientific thinking.[9] The dreams, hopes and aspirations of the people are reflected in melodies and songs. If we pay attention to national traditions and values, we will witness how ancient and developed music is in accordance with the requirements of the times, from war songs to historical creations in the form of epics. The fate of heroes like Alpomish and Gorogly has been sung in a whole new way for thousands of years. We know from history that six of the masterpieces of Shashmakom have survived to our time, and that Muhammad Ali Mashshak performed twelve maqams. So far, these masterpieces, which have played an important role in the spiritual development of Uzbeks and all Eastern peoples, are only a fragment of our musical art. The fact that the ghazals composed for Shashmakom are the wisdom of our ancestors, especially the ghazals of Navoi and other thinkers, further inspires respect for the past of our nation. We feel how great spirituality they possessed. In order for the melodies and songs created now to effectively serve our nation, it is our honorable duty to create songs that glorify patriotism, goodness, justice, and beauty, and to teach them to the new generation. The teacher is the leader in ensuring the effectiveness of music education and cultivating students' interest in musical culture lessons.

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